

D2.1 Stakeholder engagement plan

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Authors: Gabriele Ehmcke, Hanna
Kuittinen, Izaskun Jimenez Iturriza, Xabier
Uriarte Olaeta, Oliver Jancke

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Project summary

INGUMA Project aims to foster the development of bio-based materials and their acceptance by the public by relying on three main values sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics - the values of the New European Bauhaus.

The value of sustainability will be tackled by developing different types of bio-based materials from raw materials derived from agriculture residues and secondary raw materials from wood processing. Various types of materials will be developed: functionalised fibers, insulation material based on mycelium, resin-free insulation material based on wood fibers, bio-based adhesive for plywood, low-formaldehyde plywood board, wooden sandwich panels, and growth media for plants. In addition, these materials will be integrated into insulation panels and vegetated roofs.

The sustainability and circularity of these materials and solutions will be ensured by applying environmental criteria and digital tools that will allow users to make decisions on the most sustainable solutions available. Additionally, the materials will be tested according to European and international standards, as a first step in the commercialisation outside of Europe (Canada).

The value of inclusion will imply the design of co-creation laboratories that encourage collaboration among stakeholders, fostering transparent communication and generating innovative ideas. These labs will provide a platform for engagement and a structured process for stakeholders to contribute their insights and actively participate in the development of bio-based construction materials. This way, the acceptance of the developed materials, products and solutions by end-users and consumers will be maximised.

The value of aesthetics will be accomplished by co-designing and constructing a community house prototype in the rooftop of an experimental building (Derio, Spain) and as part of test houses (Savonlinna, Finland) that will use extensively the materials and products developed.

Executive summary of the deliverable

This document presents the stakeholder engagement plan for the INGUMA project. The core of it relies on a series of co-creation labs involving different stakeholders of the bio-based construction sector value chain. The objective of this co-creation approach is to smoothen the innovation pathway towards market diffusion of the INGUMA materials and products by anticipating obstacles and focusing on customer centered design. This will be achieved by integrating the solutions and feedback from the co-creation labs into the material and product development processes throughout the project. This report includes:

- Presentation of the concepts of stakeholder engagement and co-creation (Ch. 2)
- Description of the INGUMA co-creation approach for stakeholder engagement (Ch. 3), and
- Definition of guidelines for planning and organising the co-creation labs (Ch. 4).

Co-creation means involving stakeholders to become contributors of innovation process. It has proven to be successful and previous studies have identified several methods and tools that can be applied for different types of co-creation needs. For researchers, co-creation helps to align the research activities better with end-users, such as companies, societal actors, or policymakers. Similarly, for the companies, co-creation is a useful approach for ensuring that the developed solutions are meeting the needs of clients and requirements of broader stakeholder community.

In the context of INGUMA, the co-creation approach is applied to bio-based adhesive and recycling friendly plywood panels, mycelia-based thermal insulation board, resin-free thermal insulation board, structural insulation panel and substrate for growing plant vegetation on green roofs. The co-creation process considers these materials in three development phases: material kit, upscaling and demonstration; and involves stakeholders from three clusters: technical, non-technical and business. The co-creation takes a challenge-based approach targeting to provide solutions and feedback to the innovation process in a timely manner to ensure that the INGUMA materials and products are meeting the needs of end-users and broader stakeholder community. The 21 co-creation labs are organised following six steps: 1) Objective setting, 2) Identification and recruitment of the stakeholders, 3) Planning the co-creation lab, 4) Organising the co-creation lab, 5) Follow-up after co-creation lab, and 6) Reflecting and evaluating the results.

Each lab also serves as prototype and provides important feedback for improving the future co-creation labs, through continuous evaluation and adaptation of the co-creation approach. This allows for testing different methods and provides a basis for assessing the effectiveness of the co-creation approach for the material and product development. Eventually, the way the co-creation approach is set up and monitored will be documented in a guidelines document that allows others to adopt the approach in other contexts.

The results of the co-creation labs will be reported in the following deliverables of the WP2: ideation phase (D2.3) prototyping phase (D2.4) and scale-up phase (D2.5). The guidelines are tested in the international context in Canada (D2.7) and will be updated and finalised at the end of the co-creation process (D2.6).

Table of acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OI	Open Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SIP	Structural insulation panel
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

This document presents the INGUMA stakeholder engagement plan. INGUMA takes an integral approach to involve stakeholders into a series of co-creation labs supporting the development of bio-based construction materials and products in different development phases – from material research, upscaling and real-life demonstrations.

By essence, co-creation is about collaborative generation of knowledge in which INGUMA experts are working alongside with stakeholders to solve concrete challenges or receive feedback related to the materials and products developed. The involvement of stakeholders is essential to ensure that the materials and products developed are aligned with the needs and requirements of end users and other stakeholders.

INGUMA co-creation approach and guidelines presented in this deliverable are targeted to support the organisation of the co-creation labs. The co-creation approach is applied to all INGUMA innovations in different development phases, and it identifies and maps the relevant stakeholders along the construction sector value chain, grouping them to three clusters: technical, non-technical and business clusters. It also identifies relevant challenges related to the material and product development processes and maps the relevant solution provider clusters for each challenge. The plan for co-creation labs details the co-creation labs organised in each phase and allocates the responsibilities for their organisation. The guidelines are presenting practical instructions how each co-creation lab is organised. Finally, considerations related to reporting, monitoring and evaluation of the co-creation process is presented.

1.1 Context

The European Union has set an ambitious goal to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent of the world and achieving zero emissions by 2050 based on clean and circular economy². The European Green Deal is the overarching policy delivering these objectives. Apart from ambitious climate objectives, the Green Deal recognises the importance of enabling environment for delivering the objectives and making the clean transition just and fair for all by putting the people at the core of the transition, supporting the most vulnerable and affected groups.

Aligned with the European Green Deal, the updated EU industrial strategy³ envisions green and digital transition of the EU industry and its ecosystems. The Transition Pathway for Construction⁴ describes a plan for construction sector to achieve the objectives of the EU industrial strategy. The construction sector forms a second largest industrial ecosystem in Europe, bringing 9.6% value added to EU economy and offering 24.9 million jobs in the EU⁵. At the same time, the

² European Commission, The European Green Deal, A growth strategy that protects the climate. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/stories/european-green-deal/>. Accessed: June, 2024.

³ European Commission, 2021, Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a stronger Single Market for Europe's recovery. COM(2021), 350 final.

⁴ European Commission, 2023, Transition Pathway for Construction. Principal authors: Ilektra Papadaki, Philippe Moseley, Pieter Staelens, Roman Horvath, Oscar Nieto Sanz, Marina Lipari, Pablo Gutierrez Velayos, Heikki Vaananen. First edition 15 March 2023.

⁵ European Commission, 2024, Construction Industrial Ecosystem Factsheet, General publications, Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs. 24 of April, 2024. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/document/3a5c3e39-6722-4c26-8ecb-919c19640d31_en. Accessed: June, 2026.

sector is also one of the most resource intensive sectors of the economy, responsible of 37.5% of the waste in the EU. The buildings account for 40% of the EU energy consumption and 36% of the energy related greenhouse gas emissions. Against this backdrop the Transition Pathway explains the necessary building blocks for more productive practises and improved use of secondary materials. A key challenge of the sector is to improve the environmental sustainability encompassing enhanced energy efficiency and reuse and recycling of primary materials to reduce emissions across the construction sector value chains and ecosystems. This is further complicated by the complexity of the construction sector value chains, being dependent on other energy intensive ecosystems such as steel, glass, or concrete. Construction sector is a labour intensive sector, which is currently lacking skilled labour force due to retirement of ageing workers and low attractiveness of the sector for younger workers.

The success of the transition pathway depends on collaboration between the European, national, regional and local authorities, industry, academia, and citizens. The New European Bauhaus⁶ is one of the initiatives aimed to connect the actors and build together a sustainable, beautiful and inclusive future. It brings citizens, experts, businesses, and institutions together to reimagine sustainable living in Europe and creates a platform for experimentation and connection.

It is evident that the transitions in construction sector requires alignment and cooperation among many actors of the construction sector value chain. In the context of INGUMA, we aim to engage all the relevant actors of a bio-based construction material sector to the INGUMA material and product development process to ensure that they meet the needs and conditions of the different stakeholders.

1.2 Purpose and objectives of the report

The purpose of this stakeholder engagement plan is to set basis and practical guidelines for implementation of the INGUMA co-creation labs. The overall objective of the INGUMA co-creation approach is to smoothen the innovation pathway towards market diffusion of the INGUMA materials and products by anticipating obstacles and focusing on customer centered design. In particular, the co-creation labs are targeted to:

- Address technical and product specific challenges related to the material and product development carried out in WP1, WP3 and WP4.
- Deal with non-technical barriers related to policy and regulation environment and environmental and societal impacts of the bio-based construction materials.
- Ensure that the developed solutions are meeting the requirements of end-users and clients by co-creating with construction industry.

This report is the first deliverable of WP2 activities and provides detailed guidance for the rest of the activities of WP2. Particularly, for Task 2.2 Co-creation labs, which is directly implementing the co-creation approach following the guidelines specified in this report. The approach presented in this report is also used to implement a co-creation process in international context in Canada (Task 2.4). Towards the end of the project (M45), an updated version of these guidelines is presented, taking into account the experiences and lessons learnt from the implementation of the co-creation

⁶ European Union, 2024, New European Bauhaus. About the initiative. Available: https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/about-initiative_en. Accessed: June, 2024.

labs. The updated guidelines are targeted to provide support for co-creation processes in other contexts, supporting the replicability of the defined co-creation approach.

The co-creation approach is supporting the material kit (WP1), upscaling (WP3) and demonstrations (WP4) by working together with stakeholders towards solutions to concrete challenges and by provision of stakeholder feedback to the developed solutions. The co-creation will also support INGUMA's horizontal activities. The co-creation labs are contributing to sustainability and circularity assessments carried-out in WP5 by working together especially on Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). The co-creation labs are organised in close collaboration with communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities (WP6), especially in identification and recruitment of relevant stakeholders. Also, the co-creation labs with business cluster are aligned with the needs of the exploitation plan (Task 6.4) of the INGUMA project ensuring that the INGUMA innovations are better meeting the market requirements.

Taking into account the context and purpose presented above, the detailed objectives of this report are:

- To present the concepts of stakeholder engagement and co-creation (Ch. 2),
- To define and present the INGUMA co-creation approach for stakeholder engagement (Ch. 3), and
- To present guidelines for planning and organising the co-creation labs (Ch. 4).

1.3 Approach for developing the plan

To achieve the above-mentioned objectives, three activities have been carried-out:

A workshop with INGUMA partners was organised together with the Kick-off meeting at TECNALIA's premises in Derio (Spain) in January 2024. The workshop was targeted to a preliminary mapping of relevant stakeholders along the bio-based construction sector value chain and simulating a co-creation process to familiarise and enthuse the INGUMA experts about co-creation. The results of the workshop are utilised in Ch. 3 of this document for mapping the relevant stakeholder types.

Scoping interviews with INGUMA experts. Altogether 12 interviews were carried-out between 26th of April and 13th of May, 2024. The scoping interviews were targeted to INGUMA experts from *WP1: From raw materials to innovative materials kit*, *WP3: Up-scaling of the selected processes and product manufacturing* and *WP4: Demonstration of the selected solutions*, as well as experts in horizontal activities *Sustainability and circularity assessments* (WP5) and *Exploitation* (Task 6.4). The interviews had two objectives:

- To better align the co-creation labs with INGUMA innovations' development process.
- To identify specific challenges related to the material/product development process, and how these challenges could be solved with contribution of and collaboration with internal and external stakeholders in a structured co-creation process.

The one-hour interviews followed a semi-structured approach and were organised online utilising Microsoft Teams video conferencing tool. The interviews started with a preamble section in which

the basic concepts of co-creation and its role in INGUMA were presented. The preamble was followed by the actual interview including five specific questions:

1. Could you shortly describe the material/product that you are developing within INGUMA?
2. Which challenges do you foresee in the development of the material/product? (e.g. technical challenges, market challenges, social acceptance challenges, regulatory issues, other.)
3. How can these challenges be solved with the contribution of and collaboration with stakeholders external to the INGUMA project? Who are these stakeholders?
4. At which stage (referring to material kit, upscaling and demonstration) of the technological development process would you interact with external stakeholders?
 - a. What type of stakeholders would those be?
 - b. What kind of inputs could we expect from these stakeholders?
 - c. How could the external knowledge support the product/solution development? When, in terms of project schedule, the involvement of external stakeholders would be desirable?

The interviews were recorded and transcribed for supporting internal note taking, and after the interviews, a summary fiche for each interview was prepared. The insights from the interviews form the basis of the co-creation lab approach presented in Ch. 3 of this document, and especially for defining the challenges for the co-creation labs.

Presentation of the approach: The co-creation approach and guidelines were presented to the INGUMA project partners at the General Assembly meeting organised at VTT's premises in Espoo (Finland) on 25th of June, 2024. The purpose of the presentation was to receive instant feedback and comments to the co-creation approach and challenges defined. The internal scoping workshop for partners process was also organised at VTT's premises in Espoo (Finland) on 25th of June, 2024. The aim of the workshop was to understand and experience the co-creation process.

2 Stakeholder engagement and co-creation

2.1 Stakeholder engagement in research and innovation

Stakeholder engagement and management has its origins in strategic management and concerns of companies how to build a framework for handling changes in the business environment. A stakeholder is defined as “any group or individual who is affected by or can affect the achievement of an organisation’s objectives”⁷. More recently, stakeholder engagement has become widespread approach to involve different types of actors in research and innovation activities showing different manifestations and forms, depending on the perspective including:

- **Open innovation (OI)**⁸ as a term describing a process in which organisations collaborate with external stakeholders to create new ideas, products, or services;
- **Co-creation**⁹ as an innovation approach in which companies partner with customers, suppliers, or other stakeholders to co-develop and co-create value; and
- **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)**¹⁰ as a way to better engage stakeholders and their needs to publicly funded research activities.

Effective stakeholder engagement goes beyond communicating and dissemination the research and innovation results to the stakeholder community¹¹. It is about creating the channels for a reciprocal dialogue with the actors interacting with each other and putting in place right mechanisms to ensure that the interaction provides meaningful change in the research and innovation process. A successful stakeholder engagement approach engages the right stakeholders at the right time, to ensure that the research and innovation process remains grounded in real-world needs and expectations and that the innovation developed has the greatest potential when reaching the market.

Stakeholder engagement during research activities can be defined as a continuum (Figure 1 below), where the inclusivity increases from left to right¹². The first objective of stakeholder engagement is **informing** the stakeholders about the advances of the research. These activities are typically conducted as part of communication and dissemination activities of a research project including scientific publications, website, newsletter, and posts in different social media platforms to inform

⁷ Freeman and McVea, 2001, A Stakeholder Approach to Strategic Management. M. Hitt, E. Freeman, and J. Harrison (eds.) Handbook of Strategic Management, Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

⁸ Chesbrough, 2003, Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting From Technology. Harvard Business School Press, 21 (3), ISBN: 9781578518371.

⁹ Prahalad, C. K., and Venkat Ramaswamy, 2000, Co-opting Customer Competence. Harvard Business Review no. 78 (1):79-87.

¹⁰ Von Schomberg, Rene von (ed.), 2011, Towards Responsible Research and Innovation in the Information and Communication Technologies and Security Technologies Fields, Luxembourg: Publication Office of the European Union, ISBN 978-92-79-20404-3

¹¹ UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), 2024, Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, Stakeholder engagement. Available: <https://www.ukri.org/councils/epsrc/guidance-for-applicants/what-to-include-in-your-proposal/health-technologies-impact-and-translation-toolkit/stakeholder-engagement/>. Accessed: May, 2024.

¹² Utrecht University, 2024, Transdisciplinary Field Guide, Who: Stakeholder Engagement. Available: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/transdisciplinary-field-guide/in-practice/who-stakeholder-engagement>. Accessed: May, 2024.

the stakeholders about advances of the research. The second step is **consultation**, in which the stakeholders provide punctual information to the research activities at some stage of the research process. This can involve activities such as surveys, interviews or interactive workshops providing additional information or feedback from different stakeholder groups to the research process. The third step called **take advise**, the information collected from the stakeholders is actually taken into account in the research process and it contributes to a change in how the research activities are carried out. In the **co-create** step, the stakeholders are equally involved in the research and innovation activities throughout the entire research and innovation process.

Figure 1: Continuum of stakeholder involvement in research. Source: Utrecht University¹³.

2.2 Co-creation as a stakeholder engagement approach

Co-creation is inherently an innovation process that can be defined as “joint production of innovation between research, companies and possibly other stakeholders, notably civil society”¹⁴. According to OECD¹⁵, co-creation goes beyond knowledge exchange as it enables the transfer of hard to transfer tacit knowledge between the participants and brings together complementary expertise to arrive to solutions that would otherwise have been impossible. It is considered to be a powerful tool for innovation as it combines diverse expertise of different types of actors from the very beginning to feed into the innovation process, thus enhancing the applicability of research and the chances of successful innovation uptake by the market.

The European Commission (EC) also recognises the value of co-creation between academia and industry and more broadly with society. The co-creation is seen as a valuable tool for bridging the gap between the lab and the market and for boosting knowledge valorisation. “To develop new technologies, products, and services in Europe and to ensure that innovative solutions are taken up,

¹³ Utrecht University, 2024, Transdisciplinary Field Guide, Who: Stakeholder Engagement. Available: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/transdisciplinary-field-guide/in-practice/who-stakeholder-engagement>. Accessed: May, 2024.

¹⁴ OECD, 2021, Knowledge co-creation in the 21st century - A cross-country experience based policy report. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, June 2021 No. 115

¹⁵ Ibid.

academia and industry must work closely together. Strong citizen engagement is key to accelerating the uptake of innovative solutions that better respond to people's needs.¹⁶

The typical characteristics of co-creation¹⁷ include that it is industry-led or market- or societal-need driven and the co-creation activities aim to respond to the needs of future market or society. The co-creation engages societal actors such as citizens and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in different forms along the innovation value chain. The co-creation process is managed by an intermediary enabling, coordinating and bringing together the different actors. The co-creation is challenge-driven and aims to respond to a particular challenge by uniting actors in their aim to jointly develop solutions. The co-creation process can utilise digital technologies, for example to connect actors across different locations or creating interactive workspaces for the actors to collaborate.

Co-creation can be applied in different levels, e.g. in research and innovation funding programme design requesting collaboration between research and industry or research and citizens; companies' endeavours to develop new products involving end-users throughout the innovation process; or facilitating team building and collaboration among R&I project participants.

In the context of INGUMA, the co-creation approach is utilised for finding solutions to concrete challenges related to the development process of bio-based construction materials and products. The co-creation is organised as a series of 21 co-creation labs involving INGUMA internal experts and external stakeholders to work towards a solution for the concrete challenge identified. The details of the approach are presented in the following chapters of this document:

- Ch. 3 provides an overview of the co-creation approach, and
- Ch. 4 presents the guidelines for the individual co-creation lab organisation.

2.3 Methods and tools for co-creation

There are number of methods and tools for supporting co-creation process. Different tools can be used according to the expected outcomes to be obtained from the activities. There is a great variety of tools available that can be grouped according to the purpose aimed by the co-creative activity, as classified by Konrad et al. 2019¹⁸:

- Fostering empathy, supporting the understanding of a challenge from different perspectives and to engage into a dialogue to search solutions.
- Collecting ideas, targeted to wide collection of ideas.
- Structuring information, for collecting and identifying key concepts and their relations.
- Learning about needs, supporting the creation of a shared understanding about the user needs and understanding of different type of users.
- Finding solutions, is about to engage is dialogue to find solutions for real problems.

¹⁶ European Commission, 2024, New Codes of Practice for industry-academia co-creation and citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation, News article, 5 March 2024. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/new-codes-practice-industry-academia-co-creation-and-citizen-engagement-knowledge-valorisation-2024-03-05_en. Accessed: May, 2024.

¹⁷ OECD, 2021, Knowledge co-creation in the 21st century - A cross-country experience based policy report. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, June 2021 No. 115

¹⁸ Konrad, W.; Kuhn, R.; Wehner, S. & Wist, S.-K., 2019, Designing the Co-Creation Workshops. Deliverable D4.1 of EU Project 787991 "LIV_IN". Stuttgart: DIALOGIK. PID: <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-68597-3>.

- Assessing impacts, suitable for predictions and reflections of possible changes and impacts of future developments.

Figure 2: Methods for co-creation. Source: Konrad et al., 2019¹⁹.

Other methods and collection of tools considered useful for INGUMA’s co-creation labs are shortly introduced in the table below.

Table 1: Tools and methods for co-creation

Tool	Short description
The UNaLab Toolkit for co-creation (https://unalab.enoll.org/)	The UNaLab Toolkit collects user-friendly and widely applicable tools that have been applied for co-creation and experimentation of innovative solutions in a real-life urban environment together with the engagement of citizens and all relevant stakeholder groups. The toolkit including tools for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need finding: Tools to discover user needs, goals, and values to get the right solution Ideation: Tools to unleash creativity, discover valuable insights, and generate innovative solutions

¹⁹ Konrad, W.; Kuhn, R.; Wehner, S. & Wist, S.-K., 2019, Designing the Co-Creation Workshops. Deliverable D4.1 of EU Project 787991 "LIV_IN". Stuttgart: DIALOGIK. PID: <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-68597-3>.

Tool	Short description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy: Tools to design action plans to achieve long-term aims • Experimentation: Tools to test and validate the developed solution • Feedback: Tools to evaluate the user's reactions to the solution
PRISMA Responsible R&I Toolkit (https://www.rri-prisma.eu/rri-toolkit/)	PRISMA RRI toolkit supports alignment of research and innovation process to societal needs and challenges. It includes tools for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspiration and guidance, • Stakeholder engagement, • Structural change and • Technical advice.
SISCODE Toolbox (https://siscodeproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/toolkit-27092019-1.pdf)	The SISCODE Toolbox proposes four co-creation phases with different goals and results, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse context, • Reframe problem, • Envision alternatives, • Prototype and experiment.
SDG Impact Assessment Tool (https://sdgimpactassessmenttool.org/)	The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Impact Assessment Tool helps to assess how different solutions, research activities, organisations, projects, or other initiatives affect the global goals for sustainable development, including 5 steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather your forces, • Define, refine and draw the line, • Sort the SDGs • Assess your impact • Choose strategy for forward
Action Catalogue (http://actioncatalogue.eu/search)	The Action Catalogue is an online decision support tool that is intended to enable researchers wanting to conduct inclusive research, to find the method best suited for their specific project needs. It includes tools for different objectives of stakeholder participation, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dialogue, • Consulting, • Involving, • Collaborating, • Empowering, • Direct decision
iPRODUCE Co-creation methods and tools (https://iproduce-project.eu/resources-and-results/co-creation-methods-and-tools/)	A mapping and assessment of methods and tools with a strong application in Design Thinking and co-creation/co-production projects and approaches, in six categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research, • Team building, • Ideation, development, • Assessment/ evaluation, and • Validation.

Tool	Short description
GoNano Toolkits for co-creation (https://gonano-project.eu/index.html)	Collection of 14 toolkits targeted to support co-creation process, including GoNano toolkit with six steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define your goal, • Identify the stakeholders, • Start planning, • Organise your co-creation event, • Evaluate and reflect on the process, • Share the results

2.4 Co-creation success factors

To be successful the co-creation process needs to tackle a number of challenges. The following table summarises a number of success factors and INGUMA co-creation approach responses.

Table 2: Co-creation success factors and INGUMA co-creation approach

Co-creation success factors ²⁰	INGUMA co-creation approach
Clarity of scope and purpose: The boundaries and objective of the co-creation process need to be stipulated clearly to all the potential participants at early stage of the process.	INGUMA co-creation labs are based on initial scoping process and continuous scanning of challenges related to material and product development process carried-out in the project. To manage expectations correctly, the aspects that are not covered are also highlighted. Key messages are defined.
Focus on outcome: The concrete outcomes need to be clearly defined and all the actions should be targeted to concrete outcomes.	The main objective of the INGUMA co-creation labs is to achieve solutions and feedback for the INGUMA materials and products in different development phases.
Inclusiveness and representativeness: The co-creation process needs to involve the right participants to enable optimal development of collective intelligence, taking into account balance representation of different stakeholders, different expertise and background of the participants.	The INGUMA co-creation process is focusing on three clusters of solution providers, including technical, non-technical and business clusters ensuring that the views of different types of stakeholders are adequately taken into account for development of the INGUMA innovations. The participant selection for each co-creation lab takes into account different types of solution providers (e.g. different professional backgrounds, expertise, career stage, geographical location and gender) as far as it is feasible.
High-quality and fit-for-purpose: A successful co-creation process is predefined and utilises tailored methods designed for the concrete purpose as opposite to standardised tools.	The INGUMA co-creation labs follow common guidelines that are providing a predefined approach but at the same time allows tailoring the methods/tools used for the needs of the concrete challenge.
Systemic perspective: Th co-creation process needs to understand the relation and interplay of actions and actors to their context to maintain the	The INGUMA co-creation approach builds on a systemic and dynamic approach on challenge scanning, taking into account the specificities of

²⁰ OECD, 2021, Knowledge co-creation in the 21st century - A cross-country experience based policy report. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, June 2021 No. 115.

Co-creation success factors ²⁰	INGUMA co-creation approach
<p>coherence of the action and connecting the different parts to the whole.</p>	<p>each INGUMA material/product development process in different development phases (Material kit, Upscaling, Demonstration).</p>
<p>Governance and operational management: The co-creation process is hardly successful without right governance and effective operational coordination.</p>	<p>The INGUMA co-creation process forms an integral part of the project and is co-owned and participated by all the INGUMA partners. It is coordinated and operationally managed by the WP2 team. The WP2 team has clear responsibilities, planning and guidance for organising the co-creation labs.</p>
<p>Flexibility and adaptability: Although the co-creation process needs to be well designed and following fixed steps, it needs to remain flexible to adapt possibly occurring changes in the contextual setting.</p>	<p>Although the INGUMA co-creation process is predefined and structured, the continuous identification of challenges and iterative reflexions after each co-creation lab allows the approach to be adapted to the occurring changes e.g. in the innovation process or incorporating lessons learnt in a dynamic manner.</p>
<p>Transparency and openness: The co-creation process is described and documented in fully transparent and open manner, and the results of the different activities are broadly shared with the participating actors.</p>	<p>The INGUMA co-creation activities will follow fully transparent and open approach both in terms of approach, and communicating the results to the participants. The guidelines for co-creation are made publicly available and updated at the end of the project with the lessons learnt from applying the co-creation approach in the INGUMA project.</p>

3 INGUMA co-creation approach

This chapter describes the INGUMA co-creation labs, the approach used for the stakeholder engagement. The co-creation labs enable multi-level engagement and interdisciplinary involvement of different actors in order to optimise the market potential of the INGUMA products right from the start of the project. The co-creation labs are implemented as a series of 21 challenge-driven workshops.

The main objective of all workshops is a direct exchange between relevant stakeholders and INGUMA innovation developers by contributing throughout the entire process with their personal: Expertise, Experiences and Ideas. The aim is to support the product development (WP1, WP3 and WP4) to realise a co-created product, which meets the consumer needs by providing knowledge on the demands of practitioners, end users and other stakeholders. This user-centered information will be gathered within the co-creation processes, which will be facilitated through thematically focused workshops. The WP2 team will be to facilitate this process and the co-creation labs are targeted to provide solutions and feedback for the development of user-oriented and co-created materials.

The INGUMA co-creation labs aims to open-up the INGUMA material and product development process to new perspectives by inclusion of external stakeholders. The co-creation labs are:

- applied to all INGUMA innovations,
- taking into account the needs of INGUMA innovations in different development phases by defining three co-creation phases to provide timely support, and
- involving different types of stakeholders in a balanced manner.

3.1 INGUMA innovations

INGUMA project aims to develop, upscale and demonstrate bio-based construction materials and products. The project utilizes two types of secondary raw material feedstocks from agricultural residues (i.e. straw) and industrial side streams (i.e. sawdust, wood chips, wood scraps from plywood manufacturers). These feedstocks are employed to produce lignocellulosic fibers (Task 1.2) that are further elaborated in the INGUMA biomaterials kit including five bio-based construction materials:

- Bio-based adhesive and recycling friendly plywood panels (Task 1.1)
- Resin-free thermal insulation board (Task 1.3),
- Mycelia-based thermal insulation board (Task 1.4),
- Structural insulation panel (SIP) (Task 3.4), and
- Substrate for growing plant vegetation on green roofs (Tasks 1.5).

The most promising materials and technologies will be scaled-up to demonstrate the scalability of the manufacturing process (Tasks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5). The final step is to demonstrate the developed materials and products in a real environment in a community house and test houses (Tasks 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3).

The material and product development process are supported by three cross-cutting activities: co-creation labs (WP2), sustainability and circularity assessments (WP4), and communication, dissemination and exploitation (WP6).

The table below describes the INGUMA materials and products and different development phases.

Table 3: INGUMA materials and products and different development phases. The coloured dots in the first column present the different components of the innovations.

Component	Material kit	Upscaling	Demonstration
	Bio-based adhesives and recycling-friendly plywood panels (Task 1.1)		
	Lignocellulosic fibres from side-streams for applications (Task 1.2)	Upscale of lignocellulosic fibre production (Task 3.1)	
	Resin-free lignocellulosic fibres-based thermal insulation board (Task 1.3)	Upscale of resin-free lignocellulosic fibre-based thermal insulation boards (Task 3.2)	
	Mycelial based insulation board (Task 1.4)	Upscale of the manufacture of mycelia-based insulation board (Task 3.3)	
	Wood-based side streams for growing media for vegetated roofs (Task 1.5)	Upscale and assessment of a substrate for a green roof prototype (Task 3.5)	
		Upscale of structural insulation panels (Task 3.4)	
			Design of the community house in Spain (Task 4.1) Installation and monitoring of the community house in Spain (Task 4.2)
			Demonstration in a demo space in Finland (Task 4.3)
Horizontal aspects:	Sustainability & circularity assessments (WP5) Communication, dissemination and exploitation (WP6)		

3.2 Co-creation phases

As described in the previous sub-chapter, the INGUMA material and product development process has three phases: material kit, upscaling and demonstration. Accordingly, the co-creation process is divided into three different phases to meet the needs of INGUMA material and product development process in a timely manner.

Phase I: Exploration and ideation (M6-M12): The co-creation labs are focused to provide end-user requirements and solve concrete development challenges related to **material kit development** (M1-M24). The co-creation lab participants are introduced to the innovative materials and the concrete challenges identified. The stakeholder perspectives and ideation results provide initial solutions and feedback back into the material development process. 9 co-creation labs are organised online and target the different stakeholder clusters separately but in a balanced manner with the objective of organising three labs for each stakeholder group.

Phase II: Iterative prototyping and testing (M12-M36): The co-creation labs target to provide **feedback to INGUMA materials and products with already existing prototype samples** and to **address challenges related upscaling**. In addition, the co-creation labs target to give solutions and feedback to sustainability and circularity assessments (WP5) and exploitation of the INGUMA results (WP6). The 9 co-creation labs are organised as face-to-face workshops together with INGUMA General Assembly meetings (M12, M18, M24 and M30). The co-creation workshops target the three stakeholder clusters separately i.e. three workshops for each stakeholder cluster are organised.

Phase III: Scale-up (M37-M45): The Phase III co-creation labs address further market uptake of the materials, products and systems developed. The final materials and products developed are presented in the demo locations in Derio (Spain) and Savonlinna (Finland), and in one larger European workshop organised online. The co-creation labs are targeted to **receive specific feedback on materials and products developed** focusing more on the issues related to **further exploitation and market uptake**. The Phase III workshops are targeted to all the stakeholder groups in a mixed manner.

Figure 3 presents the INGUMA material and product development process and the co-creation phases to reflect the timings of each.

INGUMA material and product development process

INGUMA co-creation phases

Figure 3: INGUMA material and product development process and co-creation phases.

3.3 Identification of challenges for the co-creation labs

For the identification of concrete challenges for co-creation, 12 scoping interviews for different INGUMA experts were conducted. This chapter summarises the findings of the interviews and translates them to challenges for the co-creation labs in different phases and involving different stakeholder clusters in balanced manner.

For each of the challenges, the origin of the challenge and solution provider cluster are identified. Some of the challenges are cross-cutting by nature and the solutions of findings from the co-creation labs are benefiting the INGUMA innovations more broadly. The challenges can be categorised to three types of challenges including technical, non-technical and business challenges.

- The **technical challenges** are dedicated to seeking and provide technical solutions to INGUMA material and product development process. The solution providers can involve INGUMA partners from WP1, WP3 and WP4, external researchers and technology experts from material and construction research and related industry, or relevant technology experts from other industry sectors.
- The **non-technical challenges** are related to societal acceptance and environmental impacts of bio-based construction products, regulatory compliance and standards, role of public policy tools such as public procurement or private finance models for promoting innovative products in construction sector. These challenges are further developed in collaboration with INGUMA *WP5 Sustainability & circularity assessments* and part of the co-creation labs are organised jointly with WP5. The solution providers for non-technical challenges involve experts from regulation, standardisation, public administration, and citizens/consumer associations.
- The **business challenges** are related to market acceptance and market uptake of biobased construction products. In the exploration and ideation phase, co-creation labs are focused

on understanding the market needs, whereas in the late stages, the focus is on receiving feedback on the INGUMA products from construction sector companies.

The table below is presenting preliminary and indicative challenges for the co-creation labs. It includes:

- 10 challenges corresponding to Phase I: Exploration and ideation,
- 15 challenges corresponding to Phase II: Iterative prototyping and testing, and
- 3 challenges corresponding to Phase III: Scale-up.

The list will be continuously updated and the prioritisation and specification of the challenges will be done in collaboration with INGUMA researchers to ensure that the co-creation labs are useful and organised in timely manner reflecting the needs of the development process of the INGUMA materials and products.

Table 4: Initial list of co-creation challenges

Co-creation phase	Challenge	Challenge owner	Solution provider cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Recycled plywood: considerations of toxicity	Task 1.2 Task 1.5	A: Technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	End-user requirements for insulation materials	Task 1.4 Task 1.3	A: Technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	End-user requirements for growing media substrate	Task 1.5	A: Technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Resin removal and analytical methods for detecting resin removal	Task 1.2	A: Technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Societal acceptance of bio-based construction materials in North Europe	Cross-cutting	B: Non-technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Societal acceptance of bio-based construction materials in South Europe	Cross-cutting	B: Non-technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	New models for financing construction projects promoting innovation	Cross-cutting	B: Non-technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Public procurement as a tool for driving biobased construction sector	Cross-cutting	B: Non-technical cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Market needs for growing media substrate (ideal characteristics e.g., related to weight, thickness, granularity, compacting, water holding vs. drainage, outlook, smell, etc.)	Task 1.5 Task 3.5	C: Business cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Market needs for bio-based insulation panels (ideal characteristics e.g., for handling, installation, thermal performance, structural properties, maintenance, aesthetics, acoustics, price etc.)	Task 1.3 Task 1.4 Task 3.4	C: Business cluster
I: Exploration and ideation	Construction products market: green vs. affordable or green and affordable?	Cross-cutting	C: Business cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Energy-efficient unfreezing process – lessons from other industries	Task 3.2	A: Technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Controlling contamination and air moisture levels – lessons from other industries	Task 3.3	A: Technical cluster

Co-creation phase	Challenge	Challenge owner	Solution provider cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Feedback from lignocellulosic fibre applications	Task 1.2	A: Technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Upscaling fibre production (recycled plywood): Grinder equipment needed	Task 3.1	A: Technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Upscaling fibre production (wheat straw): Extruder producers	Task 3.1	A: Technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Upscaling fibre production (wheat straw): Enzyme producers	Task 3.1	A: Technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Upscaling insulation panel production: Mushroom producers	Task 3.3	A: Technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Regulatory compliance and standards for biobased insulation panels	Task 1.1 Task 1.3 Task 1.4 Task 3.4	B: Non-technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Regulatory compliance and standards for green roof substrate	Task 1.5 Task 3.5	B: Non-technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Environmental footprint of recycled biobased construction materials	Cross-cutting	B: Non-technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Specific questions related to Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)	Cross-cutting	B: Non-technical cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Market feedback to INGUMA prototypes: Adhesives	Task 1.1	C: Business cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Market feedback to INGUMA prototypes: Insulation boards and panels	Task 1.3 Task 1.4 Task 3.4	C: Business cluster
II: Iterative prototyping and testing	Market feedback to INGUMA prototypes: Growing media substrate	Task 1.5 Task 3.5	C: Business cluster
III: Scale-up	Feedback to INGUMA products: Derio demo (Spain)	Task 3.2 Task 3.3 Task 3.4 Task 3.5	A: Technical cluster B: Non-technical cluster C: Business cluster
III: Scale-up	Feedback to INGUMA products: Savonlinna demo (Finland)	Task 3.3 Task 3.4	A: Technical cluster B: Non-technical cluster C: Business cluster
III: Scale-up	Feedback to INGUMA products: European perspectives	Cross-cutting	A: Technical cluster B: Non-technical cluster C: Business cluster

3.4 Stakeholder characterisation

3.4.1 Construction sector value chain activities and key actors

Understanding the construction sector value chain helps identifying the key stakeholder groups. The value chain presented below covers all stages of construction materials and products life starting from supply of raw materials and finishing with material disposal after end of use²¹. The value chain includes also activities related to provision of adequate framework conditions such as financing and regulation. The value chain is comprised by the actors conducting the activities along the value chain and other relevant stakeholders that can influence the activities. Although the value chain steps are presented in a simplified and linear manner.

Figure 4 below, some of the steps can take place simultaneously or in different order and may comprise circular elements (e.g. between end-of-life and construction materials).

Figure 4: Construction sector value chain stages. Source: UN Environment Programme, 2021.

The key activities and actors of a construction sector include:

- **Financing** includes different private sector investors such as banks that can provide finance for companies or individuals. It also includes public sector funding and other type of support mechanisms (e.g. through taxation or aids) for construction sector actors.
- **Planning, design and commissioning** involves actors such as architects, urban planners, and public authorities that are responsible for construction sector planning and permissions.
- **Construction materials** includes all activities from extraction and processing raw materials to construction material and product manufacturing.
- **Logistics** is about construction material and equipment supply and sales for the construction contractors.
- **Construction** involves all the actors responsible of building or landscape construction including actors such as architects, building developers, contractors, and sub-contractors.
- **Property market** is about selling the construction and it involves actors such as property developers, the finance sector and buyers of the construction.

²¹ United Nations Environment Programme (2021). Catalysing Science-based Policy action on Sustainable Consumption and Production – The value-chain approach & its application to food, construction and textiles.

- **Operation, maintenance and renovation** is about activities needed for building or built environment to maintain or improve their intended functions.
- **End-of-life** is comprised of deconstruction, demolition and waste management after reaching the end-of-life of building or built environment.

3.4.2 INGUMA stakeholder mapping typology

For the INGUMA project, an initial stakeholder identification was carried-out in a workshop organised together with the Kick-off meeting of the project (Derio, January 2024) involving INGUMA project partners. In the workshop, the participants were asked to fill-in post-its with relevant stakeholder types for bio-based construction materials sector. After the workshop the stakeholder types were organised along the construction sector value chain and edited in terms of removing duplications. The table below presents the results of the initial stakeholder mapping.

Table 5: Value chain activities and types of stakeholders from the perspective of INGUMA.

Value chain activity	Type of stakeholders
Raw materials	Farmers, Foresters, Mechanical wood processing industry (e.g. saw mills), Mushroom growers
Finance and funding	Private sector financing (banks, investors, venture capitalist, hedge funds, etc.), Public sector funding (R&I support, subsidies and loans for companies, affordable housing support, etc.)
Research and education	Universities, Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), Vocational education and training
Planning, design, and commissioning	Architects, Engineering companies, Urban planners and developers, Local administration, Exterior and interior designers
Construction materials and equipment industry	Material manufacturing companies, Product manufacturers, Solution providers, Equipment, machinery, and tools suppliers
Logistics and distribution	Commercialisers, Distributors, Logistics companies
Construction industry	Construction companies, Landscape construction companies, Industrialised construction, Builders, Sub-contractors of construction companies
Property market	Real estate companies, Building developers, Building companies, Building and house owners
Operation, maintenance, and renovation	Maintenance companies, Building managers, Individuals
End-of-life	Demolition companies, Decommissioning and waste management companies
Policy, regulation and standardisation	Policymakers in different governance levels (EU, national, regional, local), Public administration, Authorities involved in regulation, Standardisation bodies, Certification bodies, Label organisations
Industry associations	Clusters, Industrial associations
End-users	Building and house residents, Building and house owners, Public building owners and users, Building managers, Housing, properties and residential associations
Others	Construction workers, Insurance agents, Students, Other industries, Hardware stores, Retail stores selling construction materials or furniture, Trade fair organisers, Communication and media, Influencers, Non-governmental organisations

The stakeholder mapping is an on-going activity through-out the INGUMA project duration and for collecting basic information about the stakeholder organisations, a **stakeholder mapping database** (Deliverable D2.2) is made available for INGUMA partners as a shared working document at INGUMA Teams co-working platform. The stakeholder mapping is requesting the INGUMA partners to fill-in relevant organisations with key information (name of the organisation, country, website), stakeholder type with predefined categories and reason or justification why this organisation is a relevant stakeholder for the INGUMA project activities. The database complies with all requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679.

3.4.3 Stakeholder clusters for co-creation labs

For the co-creation labs, the stakeholders are grouped in **three clusters** based on the nature of activities:

- **Technical cluster** including stakeholders that can contribute towards solving technical challenges of INGUMA material and product development process. This cluster involves research and development actors, and companies from construction sector and other industries relevant for INGUMA material and product development processes.
- **Non-technical cluster** involves stakeholders that can contribute towards improved understanding of non-technical bottlenecks of construction materials and product development related framework conditions such as policy and regulation, finance or social acceptance. This cluster includes actors such as policymakers, regulation and standardisation bodies, environmental actors or agencies, finance sector or representatives of citizens.
- **Business cluster** is about the targeted market actors or end-users of the INGUMA products and materials. These includes construction materials industry, construction developers and promoters, construction companies etc.

3.5 Timetable for the co-creation labs

The table below presents the scheduling for the co-creation labs indicating the challenge and solution provider cluster, co-creation lab, timing, venue, responsible partner and corresponding deliverable in which the results are reported. The concrete challenge for each co-creation lab (Lab 1 - Lab 21) is selected from Table 6, taking into account the co-creation phase, challenge and solution provider cluster, and prioritisation of the challenges depending on the needs and timing of the INGUMA material and product development processes.

The co-creation labs for Phase I are organised online. For Phase II, the co-creation labs are organised as face-to-face workshops and the aim is to arrange them together with the INGUMA General Assembly meetings (M12, M18, M24 and M30). In addition, relevant academic, industry and policy events are considered as options for organising the co-creation labs. In Phase III, demo locations will be used to organise face-to-face meetings mainly focusing on the involvement of end-users of construction materials.

Table 6: Timetable for the co-creation labs.

Co-creation phase	Solution provider cluster	Co-creation lab	Timing	Venue	Responsible partner	Reporting
I: Exploration and ideation	A: Technical cluster	Lab 1	M6-M12	Online	TECNALIA	D2.3 (FNR)
		Lab 2	M6-M12	Online	TECNALIA	
		Lab 3	M6-M12	Online	TECNALIA	
	B: Non-technical cluster	Lab 4	M6-M12	Online	FNR	
		Lab 5	M6-M12	Online	FNR	
		Lab 6	M6-M12	Online	FNR	
	C: Business cluster	Lab 7	M6-M12	Online	IW	
		Lab 8	M6-M12	Online	IW	
		Lab 9	M6-M12	Online	IW	
II: Prototyping and testing	A: Technical cluster	Lab 10	M13-M36	Face-to-face	TECNALIA	D2.4 (FNR)
		Lab 11	M13-M36	Face-to-face	TECNALIA	
		Lab 12	M13-M36	Face-to-face	TECNALIA	
	B: Non-technical cluster	Lab 13	M13-M36	Face-to-face	FNR	
		Lab 14	M13-M36	Face-to-face	FNR	
		Lab 15	M13-M36	Face-to-face	FNR	
	C: Business cluster	Lab 16	M13-M36	Face-to-face	IW	
		Lab 17	M13-M36	Face-to-face	IW	
		Lab 18	M13-M36	Face-to-face	IW	
III: Scale-up	A: Technical cluster B: Non-technical cluster C: Business cluster	Lab 19	M37-M45	INGUMA demo at Derio (Spain)	TECNALIA	D2.5 (TECNALIA)
	A: Technical cluster B: Non-technical cluster C: Business cluster	Lab 20	M37-M45	INGUMA demo at Savonlinna (Finland)	FNR	
	A: Technical cluster B: Non-technical cluster C: Business cluster	Lab 21	M37-M45	Online	IW	

4 Guidelines for co-creation labs

This chapter provides general instructions and guidance for organising the INGUMA the co-creation labs. They are divided into six sequential steps:

1. Objective setting
2. Identification and recruitment of the stakeholders
3. Planning the co-creation lab
4. Organising the co-creation lab
5. Follow-up after the co-creation lab
6. Evaluating and reflecting the results.

The figure below shows the causal links and feedback loops between the steps. The Step 1 is decisive as the objective of the co-creation lab influences directly the type of stakeholders to be invited (Step 2), planning of the co-creation lab (Step 3), and organisation of the co-creation lab (Step 4). After organising the co-creation lab, the results are shared with the participants (Step 5) and an internal reflection of the process and results is conducted (Step 6) and utilised for the planning of the following co-creation labs.

Figure 5: Steps for organising co-creation labs.

The following sub-chapters present each of the steps in more detailed manner.

4.1 Objective setting

The first step for organising the co-creation labs consists in the definition of the motivations and objectives of each lab. In INGUMA, this will be done through the selection of challenges already identified through scoping interviews with INGUMA experts (results of first round see Ch. 3.3, Table 4 of this document). The challenge identification will be a continuous activity, supported by periodically conducted scoping interviews to INGUMA experts. The scoping interviews already conducted serve as an initial stocktaking for challenges, especially for the co-creation labs organised in Phase I: Exploration and ideation. Another round for scoping interviews will be carried-out before launching the Phase II and Phase III co-creation labs to collect the challenges in timely manner, taking into account the advances in the material and product developments.

Once the concrete challenge is selected, it needs to be developed with challenge owners in order to describe the challenge in more detailed terms and to specify the aim of the workshop and what is expected to get out of it.

Several questions addressed to challenge owners could guide this process, such as:

- Which is the problem or challenge that you want to solve?
- Why would you want to engage with stakeholders? What would you like to know from them?
- What makes this challenge so complex?
- Why would stakeholders be interested in joining a co-creation lab and help solve the challenge?

The goals and challenges should be as concrete and detailed as possible, so that the discussions throughout the co-creation process are specific enough to enable solutions and actions to be taken by the actors involved.

4.2 Identification and recruitment of stakeholders

The identification of the co-creation lab participants is done for each co-creation lab taking into account the nature of the challenge(s) to be addressed, the phase of development of the product groups and the type of stakeholder cluster(s) to be involved in each specific lab, i.e. technical, non-technical and business.

The participants include challenge owners who are INGUMA project partners needing a solution and solution providers that can be INGUMA project partners or external actors. The scanning for solution providers is done in cooperation with the challenge owner, and includes the following steps:

- Identification of stakeholder types relevant for the challenge.
- Identification of concrete stakeholders having relevant expertise taking into account the following:
 - a) INGUMA partners' experts,
 - b) INGUMA stakeholder database,
 - c) INGUMA partners' networks,
 - d) searching suitable experts utilising social media channels e.g. LinkedIn (expert profiles) or scientific publications or conference presentations (authors).
 - e) "crowdsourcing" i.e. inviting experts through an open invitation published in INGUMA website, newsletter and in different social media channels.

Although some of the recruitment mechanisms have already been mentioned, experience shows that direct contact in person or by telephone is the most effective.

One of the key points in the recruitment of external stakeholders is to motivate them to collaborate in the co-creation labs. It is essential that they perceive the added value of interacting with other stakeholders and experts and that the topics addressed are related to their own objectives and interests. It is therefore key to identify shared goals that drive co-creation.

4.3 Planning the co-creation lab

Once the goals and relevant participants of the co-creation lab have been identified, each lab needs to be planned according to the goals that are sought to be achieved. The practical organisation needs to be carefully planned, taking into account the following aspects:

- **Team:** create an organising team that includes the co-creation lab organiser, facilitator(s) and expert(s) for internal and external communication. The role of the facilitator is key to engage participants in the right way and requires a diversity of skills, especially the capacity to create a climate of trust, empathy and collaboration.
- **Venue:** the right place for each co-creation lab needs to be selected, depending on the objective and the stakeholders engaged. Labs can be conducted in a face-to-face, online or hybrid format depending on the co-creation phase addressed. Nevertheless, the labs could be preferably hosted in the place related to the challenge addressed to bring the real-life context into view (for instance, the co-creation labs at scale-up phase could be held in the INGUMA demo sites) and bearing in mind that the chosen space should contribute to creating an atmosphere of trust, empathy and collaboration. Each format has its own advantages and disadvantages:
 - In the face-to-face format, the interaction between stakeholders is closer, the duration of the sessions is longer and the level of engagement of the participating stakeholders is higher. On the other hand, it is more complicated to recruit participants because it means a higher level of involvement (travel and more time dedicated to the lab).
 - In the online format it is somewhat easier to adjust agendas, although the freshness of face-to-face interaction with other participants is lost and the level of involvement of the face-to-face sessions is not reached.
 - The hybrid format has the advantages and disadvantages of the previous formats depending on whether participants attend in person or online but has the disadvantage that interaction between the two groups (face-to-face and online) is more difficult.
- **Resources:** the organisation of the event will require financial, time and social resources. A budget might be necessary to rent a space according to the requirements of the lab, to provide catering or to reimburse travel costs to participants if that is needed. Also, the time needed to organise and conduct the lab needs to be considered since co-creations is a time intensive process. Finally, support material for online labs (for example, ppt presentation, Miro board, etc) and face-to-face labs (for example ppt, post-its, prototypes of INGUMA innovations, boards etc.) need to be foreseen.
- **Ethical and privacy aspects:** since the organisation of the co-creation labs require contacting different stakeholders and collecting their personal data, a GDPR strategy needs to be in place. INGUMA's ethics and data management policies will be followed.

4.4 Organising the co-creation lab

As mentioned in section 2.3 of this document, there are many methods and tools to design and organise a co-creation lab. In INGUMA we structured the labs focusing on different phases of co-

creation based on the development phase of the INGUMA innovations (i.e. exploration and ideation; iterative prototyping and testing; scale up). Each of these phases will require a tailor-made approach to the lab and choosing the right methods for the co-creation labs depends on the goals set the desired outcomes, the type of participants engaged in each lab and potential IPR concerns at stake. Methods need to address the need of establishing connections and exploring synergies among the participants and enabling the collaboration between stakeholders coming from different backgrounds. Methods will be tailored to the different phases of the co-creation labs and to the different stages of each lab, for example:

1. Starting with a round of introduction of participants.
2. Following with an ice-breaker exercise to allow all participants get to know each other
3. Posing challenges and set smaller groups to discuss and share perspectives and solutions
4. Sharing insights in plenary to share views, find consensus or identify conflicting views
5. Developing a vision and steps to implement the ideas raised into the innovations' development
6. Providing a framework for networking at the end of the lab, allowing participants expand their professional network.

4.5 Follow-up after the co-creation lab

Communication and dissemination are essential to keep internal and external stakeholders engaged and to be able to attract others to INGUMA's co-creation process, in addition to sharing the results of the process with wider audiences. Due to the iterative character of INGUMA's co-creation process, which relays on the engagement of stakeholders during a long period of time, it is key to quickly follow up and report to stakeholders after each lab. Sharing and communication at all phases of the process will allow maintaining the communication, collaboration and trust channels built during each co-creation lab.

Therefore, after each co-creation lab, each INGUMA team in charge of organising the event, will hold an internal meeting to reflect and discuss on the process and results of the lab. These conclusions will be reported to all the participants of the lab, trying to provide an accurate picture of what happened in the labs, its outcomes and next steps. In addition, the findings and results obtained during the whole process can be translated into narratives for wider audiences if confidentiality and privacy is maintained. Different channels can be used depending on the audience: face-to-face meetings at conferences, networking events, websites, social media, etc.

4.6 Evaluating and reflecting the results

The evaluation of the co-creation process will be a dynamic, on-going activity though out the co-creation process. To fully understand the success of co-creation different types of evaluation are needed. To assess the success of co-creation, process different types of indicators can be used, including quantitative, such as targeted number and type of different stakeholders compared to

involved stakeholders, or qualitative, taking into account for example, the transparency of the process, accountability or ownership by the participants²².

The evaluation of the INGUMA co-creation labs includes reflections from three perspectives. First, it takes into account the feedback of the co-creation lab participants. Secondly, it includes evaluation of usefulness of the results achieved by the challenge owners or recipients of the results. Thirdly, an auto-reflection is done by the lab organisers to identify aspects for improvement of the INGUMA Co-creation approach. This reflective evaluation concept supports the co-creation process with its iterative nature delivering valuable insights to the planning and organisation of the following co-creation labs.

The evaluation is supported by a feedback questionnaire provided to the co-creation lab participants after each lab. Indicative topics to be included to the questionnaire are presented in the Table 7 below.

Table 7: Evaluation questionnaire concept for participants of the co-creation workshop.

Part	Description
Overall experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance and clarity of the objectives
Workshop facilitation, quality and usefulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectiveness of the facilitators, time management • Quality of the outputs • Usability of the results
Activities and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement and relevance
Implementation potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasibility of the recommendations • Implementation capacity
Outputs and outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction and actionability
Impact and follow-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected impact • Act on the results
Participant feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most valuable part? • Improvements? • Any new insights, knowledge, or skills? Please elaborate. • Additional comments or suggestions

4.7 Reporting

The reporting of the co-creation labs is done at the end of each co-creation phase as shown in the table below. The reporting will include summaries of each co-creation labs including characterisation of the challenges, participants, lab organisation (e.g. methods used, venue), results achieved, and feedback received from the participants. The reporting will include also an overall reflexions and lessons learnt collectively from all the co-creation labs organised in each phase.

²² Meister Broekema, P., Bulder, E., Horlings, L. G., 2023, Evaluating co-creation in social innovation projects: Towards a process orientated framework for EU projects and beyond, *Research Evaluation*, Volume 32, Issue 2, April 2023, Pages 286–298, <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvad017>

Table 8: Reporting of the co-creation process

Co-creation phase	Number of co-creation labs	Deliverable	Timing	Responsible partner
I: Exploration and ideation	9	D2.3	M12	FNR
II: Prototyping and testing	9	D2.4	M36	FNR
III: Scale-up	3	D2.5	M45	TECN

In addition, the findings and results obtained during each phase and the whole process can be translated into narratives for wider audiences if confidentiality and privacy is maintained. Different channels can be used depending on the audience: face-to-face meetings at conferences, networking events, websites, social media, etc.

5 Conclusions

Co-creation is a novel way of innovating that involves making changes to the traditional way of conceiving, designing, and developing new products. As with any new way of working, co-creation can face barriers or scepticism when implemented into practice. That is why it is essential to describe and define the meaning, scope and possibilities co-creation offers in a transparent and clear manner.

The development of the co-creation approach for INGUMA was a co-creative process itself, involving not only the WP2 team but all the INGUMA partners. The INGUMA partners have been particularly important for defining the stakeholder typology and identification of challenges for the co-creation labs. Although some of the INGUMA partners admitted that they are rather unfamiliar with co-creation concept and many said it is the first time they are participating in a co-creation process, overall, the co-creation was positively received, and the INGUMA partners showed an open and constructive attitude towards co-creation. The identification of co-creation lab challenges showed that:

- Technical knowledge for INGUMA innovations is largely available within the consortium, non-technical and business expertise is more needed.
- In respect to technical activities, co-creation is considered to be more important with closer to market activities than lower TRL-levels.
- Structured and guided co-creation process among the INGUMA partners can be relevant as they are the key stakeholders for the products developed and together, they form important parts of the value chains.
- The need for involvement of externals varies between products and development phases and can include stakeholders beyond the construction sector value chain.
- Co-creation comes with limits - the characteristics of the materials/products developed can be openly discussed with external stakeholders, but not always the process for developing them.
- Co-creation is an iterative process and similarly, the challenge identification should be seen as continuous or repetitive process, considering the advances in the product and process developments.

The guidelines for co-creation set common boundaries and instructions for organising the co-creation labs. At the same time, they are open and flexible enough to be updated to the needs of INGUMA material and product development processes. The guidelines are targeted to ensure that the co-creation becomes an integral part of the INGUMA project, and it truly contributes towards improved bio-based, circular innovations for construction industry that are better aligned with the needs and requirements of end users and other stakeholders.

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